

Exploring Y-DNA haplogroup diversity in the British Isles

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Abstract

The Yfiler™ Plus PCR Amplification Kit is a Y-chromosome STR kit designed for the specific amplification of male DNA samples. This makes it particularly useful in sexual assault cases and paternal lineage studies. Additionally, the high inter-population variability of Y-STRs makes the kit ideal for investigating biogeographical differences and migration patterns. The aim of this study was to investigate the haplogroups of the English, Irish, Welsh, and Scottish populations to support the development of population-specific Y-STR databases and advance our understanding of the genetics of the British Isles. Buccal swabs were collected from 888 unrelated male individuals: 461 English, 191 Irish, 124 Welsh, and 112 Scottish. DNA was extracted using Prep-n-Go™ Buffer and amplified with the Yfiler™ Plus kit. The resulting data passed the Y Chromosome Haplotype Reference Database (YHRD) quality checks and were uploaded to the database. Haplogroups were identified using the Y-DNA Haplogroup Predictor - NevGen online tool, and haplogroup diversity was calculated. A total of 46 haplogroups were observed, with R1b M269 being the most common haplogroup across all populations (64% in English, 85% in Irish, 92% in Welsh, and 73% in Scottish). I1 was the second most common haplogroup in both the English (13%) and Scottish (6%) populations, while I2a2a M223 was the second most common in the Welsh (2%) and Irish (6%) populations. R1a M198 and E1b1b > V13 were the other two most frequently observed haplogroups, while the remaining 41 haplogroups were found five or fewer times across all populations. Although the Scottish population showed a higher number of haplogroups relative to the sample size tested, greater diversity was observed in the English (0.57) and Scottish (0.46) populations compared to the Irish (0.28) and Welsh (0.14) populations. This study highlights genetic differences between the four populations, with the distribution of haplogroups supporting previous findings. However, further studies with more markers and larger sample sizes are needed to continue populating Y-marker databases.

Keywords

Yfiler™ Plus PCR Amplification Kit, Y-STRs, Y haplogroups, population genetics, British Isles, haplogroup diversity.

Introduction

The Yfiler™ Plus PCR Amplification Kit is a multiplex kit that detects 27 Y-chromosome Short Tandem Repeat (Y-STR) loci [1]. As the Y chromosome is passed from father to son across generations and is absent in females, it is particularly useful in several forensic applications. For example, in sexual assault cases, Y-STR testing can isolate male DNA, identifying the paternal lineage of the perpetrator. It is also valuable in relationship testing and in the identification of missing persons and victims of mass disasters.

The male-specific region of the Y chromosome is inherited as a linkage block without recombination. However, mutations occurring during male gamete production accumulate across generations, leading to significant inter-population variability. These features make the study of Y markers ideal for investigating biogeographical differences and migration patterns [2-3].

Haplogroups, which represent shared paternal lineage and common ancestry, are defined by specific markers and named using an alphanumeric notation system. They are classified in phylogenetic trees, which are used for demographic studies. Y haplogroups are typically defined by Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs), while Y-STR linkage groups are referred to as haplotypes [4]. Several Y-haplogroup predictor tools have been developed to infer haplogroups from Y-STR profiles [5].

Since haplotypes and haplogroups are characterised by multiple linked markers, their population frequencies cannot be derived from individual allelic frequencies using the product rule. Therefore, it is essential to continually populate databases with data from various populations to identify rare profiles and support accurate statistical calculations [6].

This study aimed to investigate the Y haplogroups of English, Irish, Welsh, and Scottish populations to aid in the development of population-specific Y-STR databases and enhance understanding of the genetic structure of the British Isles.

Material studied, methods, techniques

Study samples

Following the collection of informed consent, buccal swabs were taken from 888 unrelated male individuals who self-identified their ethnicity as being from various regions of the British Isles: 461 English, 191 Irish, 124 Welsh, and 112 Scottish.

DNA extraction and Y-STR typing

DNA was extracted using the Prep-n-Go™ Buffer (Applied Biosystems™) [7] and amplified with the Yfiler™ Plus PCR Amplification Kit (Applied Biosystems™), following the manufacturer's instructions. Capillary electrophoresis was performed on the ABI Prism® 3500xL Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems™), and profiles were analysed using GeneMapper® ID-X v1.6 software (Applied Biosystems™).

Data analysis

All obtained Y-STR profiles passed the quality checks of the Y-Chromosome STR Haplotype Reference Database (YHRD) [8] and were uploaded to the database (submission accession numbers: YA005979-1 for English, YA005879-1 for Irish, YA006006-1 for Welsh, and YA006005-1 for Scottish). Haplogroups were determined using the Y-DNA Haplogroup Predictor - NevGen online tool [9]. Haplogroup diversity was calculated in Excel using the formula $n(1 - \sum p_i^2) / (n-1)$, where p_i is the frequency of the i^{th} haplogroup, and n is the total number of samples [10].

Results

All samples produced unique Y-STR haplotypes. The NevGen prediction revealed a total of 46 haplogroups, with R1b M269 being the most common group across all four populations (Figure 1). The second most common haplogroup was I1 in the English and Scottish populations, while I2a2a M223 was more frequent in the Welsh and Irish samples. I2a2a M223 was also the third most common haplogroup in the English dataset. Overall, R1b M269 was observed in 73% of the samples, I1 in 8%, I2a2a M223 in 5%, followed by R1a M198 (3%) and E1b1b > V13 (2%). The remaining 41 haplogroups were found fewer than six times each across all populations (<0.6%).

Figure 1: Pie charts representing the frequency of the main haplogroups identified among the English, Irish, Welsh, and Scottish population samples.

The Welsh population, with over 90% of individuals belonging to R1b M269, exhibited the lowest diversity (Table 1). The Irish dataset showed the second lowest haplogroup diversity, followed by the Scottish and English populations. In comparison to the others, the Scottish population displayed a higher number of haplogroups relative to the sample size tested.

Table 1: Sample size, number of observed haplogroups, and haplogroup diversity for each population tested.

Population	Sample Size	Observed Haplogroups	Haplogroup Diversity
English	461	34	0.57
Irish	191	12	0.28
Welsh	124	9	0.16
Scottish	112	16	0.46

Discussion

The results suggest the presence of genetic differences in the Y chromosome across the four populations of the British Isles tested. R1b M269, also referred to as R1b1a2 (R-M269), a subclade of haplogroup R1b, has previously been reported as the major lineage in Western Europe [11-12]. There is a gradient of increasing prevalence towards the west, from 12% in eastern Turkey to 85% in Ireland, with approximately 110 million European men carrying this haplogroup. The time to the most recent common ancestor (TMRCA) was also estimated, with the oldest value recorded in central Turkey (7,989 years [95% confidence interval (CI): 5,661–11,014]) and the youngest in Cornwall (5,460 years [3,764–7,777]) [12]. Some populations in Cornwall and Wales have also been observed to be fixed for the R1b haplogroup [13], which aligns with the findings of the present study.

The I1 haplogroup, also known as I-M253, has been identified as a native European haplogroup associated with Germanic migrations, with a higher prevalence in England compared to other regions of the British Isles [14]. This haplogroup is also found in 37-39% of Swedish [15], Norwegian [16], and Danish [17] males, making it a useful marker for “invaders”, such as the Vikings or Anglo-Saxons. As observed in this study, previous research has shown a higher frequency of I1 in England compared to other parts of the British Isles [13].

Overall, a significant patrilineal population structure has been observed in areas influenced by Anglo-Saxon migration [13]. Similarly, genetic data suggests that the eastern part of the British Isles, particularly England, has experienced increased genetic influence due to multiple migrations and invasions, including those of the Anglo-Saxons [18]. Conversely, Ireland, Wales, and Scotland are believed to have retained a higher proportion of original Celtic DNA. The Welsh gene pool, in particular, is thought to be the closest to that of the first settlers who arrived in Britain after the last Ice Age [19]. As expected, this study shows greater Y haplogroup diversity in the English dataset compared to other areas of the British Isles, while the Welsh population exhibits the lowest diversity, followed by the Irish and Scottish populations.

While this study confirms previous findings and highlights the need for separate databases to perform statistical calculations related to Y-STRs, some limitations should be noted. Firstly, the small size of the datasets, particularly for the Irish, Welsh, and Scottish populations, may have affected the observations and skewed the percentages. Secondly, the accuracy of the haplogroup predictions may have been impacted by the prediction tool used. Inaccurate estimates have been

reported when using 19 Y-STRs to predict haplogroups with various prediction tools, including NevGen [5]. A combination of STRs and SNPs, with a higher number of markers, may yield more accurate haplogroup determinations and should be considered for future studies [4].

Conclusion

This study highlights the differences between Y haplogroups in the four populations of the British Isles, reaffirming the need to establish local Y-STR databases for the English, Irish, Welsh, and Scottish populations. While the distribution of haplogroups supports previous findings, further studies with more markers and larger sample sizes are required to continue populating Y-marker databases and to ensure the most accurate results. A population-specific Y-STR database would be invaluable in both legal cases (e.g., paternity or criminal cases) and historical studies tracing lineage and migration. This would significantly expand the application of Y chromosome testing, particularly in forensics, genealogy, and historical research.

Conflict of interest statement

All claims made in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of their affiliated company or organisation.

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